

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Pharmacotherapy III**

Level: **5th Class, 1st Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 3 hours.**

Reference Text:

1- Joseph T. DiPiro, Robert L. Pharmacotherapy: A Pathophysiologic Approach. Latest edition.

2- Mary Anne koda-kimble (ed.), Applied Therapeutics: The clinical use of drugs. Latest edition.

3- Marie A. Chisholm-Burns. Pharmacotherapy Principles & Practice. Latest edition.

Objective:

The course provides students with basic knowledge about pathophysiology, symptoms and aims of treatment. In addition to the basic knowledge on the drug's use, kinetics drug interactions, dose calculations, side effects, treatment algorithms and patient awareness. The diseases of the following topics will be covered: Neurologic Disorders, Psychiatric Disorders, Gynecologic and Obstetric Disorders, and Dermatologic Disorders.

No	Lecture title	hours
1.	Thyroid and parathyroid disorders	2
2.	Contraception	1
3.	Endometriosis	1
4.	Menstruation related disorders	1
5.	Hormonal replacement therapy (HRT)	2
6.	Cancer treatment and chemotherapy	2
7.	Leukemias	3
8.	Lymphomas and Multiple myeloma	2
9.	Breast and prostate cancers	2
10.	Adverse effects of chemotherapy	2
11.	Human immunodeficiency virus	2
12.	Adrenal gland disorders	1
13.	Pituitary gland disorders	1
14.	Alzheimer's disease	1

15.	Schizophrenia	2
16.	Depressive disorders	2
17.	Anxiety disorders	1
18.	Sleep disorders	1
19.	Bipolar disorders	2
20.	Colorectal cancer	1
21.	Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder	2
22.	Autism Spectrum Disorders	2
23.	Supportive Care in Oncology	3
24.	Skin Cancer	2
25.	Palliative Care	2
26.	Psoriasis	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

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Title of the course: **Case study in therapeutics III**

Level: **5th Class, 1st Semester**

Credit hours /week: Theory 3 hours

Reference:

1-Soraya Dhillon. pharmacy case studies. Latest edition.

2- Linda J Dodds. Drugs in Use Clinical case studies for pharmacists. Latest edition.

3-Mary Anne koda-kimble (ed.), Applied Therapeutics: The clinical use of drugs. Latest edition.

4-David M. Angaran, Karen L. Whalen. Medication therapy management : a comprehensive approach. Latest edition.

Objective:

During this course, the students will use clinical cases to develop the students' ability to assess patients' conditions, determine reasonable treatment alternatives, select appropriate therapy and monitoring parameters, and to justify those choices by utilizing knowledge & skills acquired in therapeutics.

No	Lecture title	Hours
1.	Case studies about Thyroid and parathyroid disorders	3
2.	Case studies about Contraception	3
3.	Case studies about Menstruation related disorders	3
4.	Case studies about Hormonal replacement therapy	3
5.	Case studies about Supportive Care in Oncology	3
6.	Case studies about Lymphomas	3
7.	Case studies about Leukemias	3
8.	Case studies about Breast cancers	3
9.	Case studies about Colorectal cancer	2
10.	Case studies about Palliative Care	2
11.	Case studies about Schizophrenia	3
12.	Case studies about Depressive disorders	3
13.	Case studies about autism spectrum disorders	3
14.	Case studies about sleep disorders	2
15.	Case studies about Alzheimer's disease	2
16.	Case studies about Psoriasis	2
17.	Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs)	2

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: Advanced Pharmacy Practice Experience **I**

Level: **5th Class, 1st Semester**

Credit hours: **Laboratory 16**

Reference Text:

Manuals prepared by the Clinical Pharmacy Department.

Objective:

During the Advanced Pharmacy Practice Experience (clerkship), students will be involved in the provision of advanced clinical pharmacy services in various medical sub-specialty environments in

specialized centers(units). The student will have experience of responsibilities (under direct supervision of preceptor). The following topics will be covered:

Internal medicine (cardiology, gastroenterology, respiratory and endocrinology), Critical care, Neurology and Psychiatry.

No	Rotation name	weeks	Credit
1	Internal medicine I	8	4
2	Internal medicine II	8	4
3	Critical care and emergency medicine	8	4
4	Psychiatry and Neurology	8	4
Total credits of 1 st semester			16

Graduation project

Practical 4 hr. / week, 2 credit hr.